

Mapping of forest roads to support touristic activities

Introduction

Mapping forest roads is important for various aspects related to sustainable forest management. In the context of guiding forestry companies towards multifunctionality beyond just production, especially if aiming for certification under PEFC and FSC standards for forest services, it is necessary to map and keep records of other indicators, including forest road infrastructure and their functionality. In this context, expediting the mapping of existing forest roads and identifying potential issues is crucial for intervention.

From a tourism and accessibility perspective, it is also essential to determine which means of transportation can be used on these roads (walking, biking, accessibility for people with disabilities). In this context, GO-SURF, in its test areas, used GNSS receivers to map existing roads and classified them based on their functionality, thereby preliminarily identifying existing and potentially accessible routes, while also identifying any maintenance issues.

The result led to the mapping of the existing road network and its condition, which is a prerequisite for identifying additional trails to open up within the forest.

Lessons learned

Using low-cost GNSS receivers and/or mobile app development, it is indeed possible to map forest road infrastructure quite easily. Unfortunately, due to a lack of management over the past 30 years, some of the old routes and trails have been lost in certain areas. This discrepancy has resulted in a reduced level of existing and usable road infrastructure for tourism purposes compared to what was expected based on regional technical maps.

However, looking to the future, with the assistance of GNSS receivers, it will be possible to identify additional potential routes to be opened up.

For further information contact

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Further information

<https://www.go-surf.it/>

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